

Spectrophotometric Study of Zirconium-Solochrome Cyanin R Complex

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The nature of Zirconium-SCR complex was studied using spectrophotometric and kinetic techniques. At pH 1.6, this complex has a composition 2 : 1 (metal : reagent) at 540 nm. The rate of reaction was found to be of 2nd order, inversely proportional to the square of hydrogen ion concentrations, thus confirming the existence of $Zr(OH)_2^{2+}$ as complex forming specie. The thermodynamic stability constant was calculated to be 1.2×10^{10} at 30° . The optimum conditions for the spectrophotometric determinations were also calculated at pH 1.6 and the SCR is suggested to be a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of zirconium.

The reagent solochrome cyanine R, is chemically known as trisodium salt of 5-[α -(3-carboxy 5-methyl-4-oxo-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1-ylidene)-2-sulfobenzyl]-3-methyl salicylic and abbreviated as SCR in these studies. The carboxylic groups attached to different benzene rings having one phenolic and one quinoid groups in orthopositions, help the chelation with quite a few metal ions¹⁻⁵. The zirconium is well known for its preference towards —COOH group as was shown in different oxalate complexes. Colorimetric determination of hafnium in presence of zirconium was also reported⁶. Babko and others⁷⁻⁸ have suggested SCR as one of the reagents for the colorimetric determination of zirconium.

Besides the scanty literature available on the determination of zirconium using SCR in different conditions, no work seems to have been done on nature of complexes formed, the equilibrium involved, the calculation of stability constants and the structure of complex formed. The present paper deals with all the above points.

EXPERIMENTAL

Absorbance measurements were made with Spectronic-20 colorimeter, pH measurements were done with Elico model direct reading pH meter with glass-calomel electrode system. Ion exchange and electrophoresis experiments have been done to find out the charge over the complex.

Stock solution of zirconium oxychloride was prepared by dissolving its known weight in 1M HCl solution and kept for 24 hrs before use. The zirconium content was estimated as zirconium pyrophosphate. Standard solution of pure sample of SCR (B.D.H.) was made by dissolving known weight of the reagent in distilled water. The reagent purity was tested by usual methods⁹. Sodium perchlorate solution was used for adjusting the ionic strength. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

Conditions of study : The volume of mixtures prepared, were kept 25 ml. in each case. The pH was adjusted at constant level by the addition of suitable amount of HCl carefully. There was no effect on changing the order of addition of reagents. However, in all cases SCR was added to zirconium solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of pH on SCR solution : It was studied in the entire visible range, i.e. 400 to 620 nm. The results show the λ_{\max} of the reagent to remain 480 nm between 1-2 pH, 520 nm between 2.5 to 3.5 pH, 530 nm between 4.5-6.5, 430 nm between 7-11.5 pH and 580 nm between 12.0-13.0 pH.

The acid dissociation constants of SCR may be represented as $H_4R \xrightleftharpoons{k_1} H_3R^{1-} \xrightleftharpoons{k_2} H_2R^{2-} \xrightleftharpoons{k_3} HR^{3-} \xrightleftharpoons{k_4} R^{4-}$. The values of different pK 's calculated spectrophotometrically are 4.1, 7.1, 12.5. The one-SO₃H group dissociates at much lower pH.

Absorption Spectra of Zirconium-SCR Complex : To find the nature and number of complexes formed, absorption spectra was taken in the entire visible range at different pH values, with different ratios of metal to ligand concentrations. It was found that only one complex having λ_{\max} of 540 nm forms between pH 1.0 to 2.0. Between 3.0 to 6.0 the λ_{\max} varies from 520 to 540 nm in different ratios of mixtures. The number of complexes formed between pH 1.0 to 3.0 was further confirmed by taking the absorption spectra of mixtures containing metal : reagent in 60 : 1 ratio, at different pH values at minute pH intervals. The graph shows two λ_{\max} 540 and 560 nm with one isosbestic point giving inflection at 550 nm revealing the existence of only one complex (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Zr-SCR complex with 60 : 1 (metal - reagent) at various pH values.

Concentration of SCR = $2 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Concentration of metal = $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$.

pH of different curves from A to H = 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 2.0, 2.4, 2.8, 3.2, 3.8 respectively.

Composition of Complex : Studies at pH 1.6 and at λ_{\max} 540 and 560 nm revealed the existence of 2 : 1 (metal : reagent) complex. However, because of variations in λ_{\max} the study of the composition at pH 4.0 was also done and it was found that at 580 nm the 2 : 1 complex again dominates, whereas at 540 and 560 nm the readings were not found to be systematic.

Kinetics of Zirconium SCR Reaction : In order to investigate the reacting zirconium species, the reaction kinetics of the complex was studied spectrophotometrically at different pH values and at 540 nm. It was found that the complex does not form below pH 1.0; at pH 1.0 the complex formed after 24 hrs, whereas at pH 1.6 it takes about 15 min, and at pH 2.0 less than 10 mins. It may thus be inferred that in weakly acidic media the reaction between zirconium and SCR is rapid, but becomes very slow at high acid concentrations. The dissociation of SCR may also affect the rate at high acidity. The kinetics of this reaction was followed spectrophotometrically as shown in Table 1 at pH 1.6.

TABLE 1

*Rate of reaction of complex at pH 1.6; λ_{max} 540 nm. Concentration of metal = $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$;
Concentration of reagent = $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$*

Time (in sec.)	0	30	60	120	180	240	300	900	∞
Absorbance (A)	0.08	0.190	0.210	0.225	0.235	0.240	0.245	0.275	0.275
$(A_{\infty} - A)$	—	0.085	0.065	0.050	0.040	0.035	0.030	0.000	0.000
$\frac{1}{(A_{\infty} - A)}$	—	12.0	15.0	20.0	25.0	29.0	40.0	—	—

It was found that the reaction obey closely 2nd order kinetics, i.e. plot of $\frac{1}{A_{\infty} - A}$ vs. time being linear as shown in fig. 2. The reaction rate was increased considerably by increasing the zirconium concentration but increasing SCR concentration has very little effect on reaction rate. It may be concluded from this that SCR does not react with Zr^{4+} but with hydrolysed zirconium specie, and therefore the hydrolysis reaction is the rate determining step.

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/(A_{\infty} - A)$ vs. Time in seconds to show second order reaction at pH 1.6 and λ 540 nm.

Concentration of metal = $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

Concentration of reagent = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Complexing Equilibria : On the basis of above studies the equilibrium between zirconium and SCR can be written as :

making the 2 : 1 (Metal : Ligand) complex neutral in nature. The neutral nature of the chelate was confirmed experimentally through electrophoresis and ion-exchange experiments.

Stability Constants of the Complex : The stability constant values have been calculated by the three different methods as shown in Table 2. The value of thermodynamic stability constant was then evaluated by plotting the ionic strength vs. average value of $\log K$ and then by extrapolating this to zero ionic strength. The value comes out to be 1.2×10^{10} .

TABLE 2

Stability constant of Zr-SCR complex at pH 1.6, $\lambda = 540$ nm. Temp. 30°

μ	Values of $\log K$			Average value of $\log K$
	Dey <i>et al</i> ¹⁰	Mole ratio	Job's nonequimolar	
0.1	9.94	10.06	9.96	9.99
0.2	9.87	9.98	9.90	9.91
0.3	9.63	9.90	9.84	9.79
0.4	9.56	9.81	9.76	9.71

Analytical Applications of the Reactions : The reddish violet colour produced by the reaction of zirconium with SCR at pH 1.6 ± 0.2 can suitably be utilized for the spectrophotometric determination of small amount of zirconium, at 540 nm. The colour formation was complete within 15 mins. but mixtures were kept for half an hour for equilibration. The maximum colour formation was only attained when the mixture contained greater than four fold excess of the reagent. The range of adherence to Beer's law was found from 0.9 to 7.3 ppm of zirconium. However, the range for most effective photometric determination was calculated to be 1.5 to 7.0 ppm of zirconium. Temperature has no effect on absorbance value from 25° to 45°.

Sandell sensitivity for the colour reaction was calculated to be $0.057 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The average value of the molar absorptivity at pH 1.6, at λ_{max} 540 nm is 30,000. Common anions do not interfere at all concentrations, however the interference by tartrate, oxalate, and citrate were significant. The cations which do not interfere were Th^{4+} , TiO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , WO_4^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , etc., whereas the Hf^{4+} , Fe^{3+} interfere and hence their absence is to be checked before adopting this procedure. The sensitivity, stability, reproducibility and lesser interference by other ions in these conditions are worth mentioning.

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